

JOSHI EFFECT IN BENZENE VAPOUR UNDER X-RAYS. PART I. INFLUENCE OF EXCITING POTENTIAL

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Joshi effect in benzene vapour under X-rays, in an ozoniser discharge, is studied due to 50 cycle potentials in the range 7–20 kV. The range of potential (V) studied consists of (a) 0–7.4 kV *i.e.* well below V_m , the 'threshold potential' (8 kV), the current being capacitive and unaffected by X-rays; (b) 7.4–7.95 kV where the discharge is not 'self maintained', a large reversible positive Joshi effect is observed; (c) a narrow region 7.95–7.68 kV characterised by an irreversible $+\Delta i$; (d) a region of 'self-maintained' discharge 8–20 kV wherein $-\% \Delta i$, maximum near V_m is observed. The results are explained by an extension of Joshi's theory associating $-\Delta i$ with the space charge effect due to negative ions, to a consideration of the behaviour of the positive ionic space charge.

Arising out of Joshi's observation (*Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 278) of the producibility of a large negative Joshi effect ($-\Delta i$) in chlorine gas on exposure to X-rays, a powerful means of ionisation, its observation in other systems was investigated by a number of workers (Asolkar, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1951, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abs. No. 69, 70; Bhiday, *ibid.*, 1950, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 58; Bhide, *ibid.*, 1951, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 39, 40; Saxena and Karmalkar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1950, 19, 276; Bhide, *ibid.*, 1951, 20, 182). Non-occurrence of $\pm \Delta i$ in electrically excited benzene under both visible and ultraviolet suggested the desirability of the present extension of the preliminary work.

EXPERIMENTAL

Well purified benzene vapour in equilibrium with liquid phase at 27° corresponding to the pressure $p=105$ mm. was excited by a 50 cycle transformer discharge in the annular space of Siemens' all glass ozoniser. The general experimental set up was similar to that developed by Joshi (*Benaras Hindu Univ. J.*, 1950). The discharge current i was measured with a mirror galvanometer actuated by RCA 30 triode used as a diode coupled resistively with the ozoniser. A radiator type Coolidge tube with a tungsten target was the source of X-rays. The voltage on the X-ray tube (anode voltage) was taken as a measure of the penetrating power of the radiation (Rutherford, Barnes and Richardson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 30, 339).

The anode current indicated the intensity of the radiation (Rutherford, *ibid.*, 1917, 34, 201). The ozoniser was enclosed in a lead-lined chamber, with a lead shutter movable by a pulley. The ozoniser current i at a given exciting potential V , was measured when it was shielded from X-rays (i_b) and when exposed to it (i_t). The difference $i_b \sim i_t$ gave the net Joshi effect Δi and its relative value $100 \times \Delta i / i_b$, under X-rays of a given intensity I , in terms of tube current and hardness as anode voltage in kV. The wave form of the discharge current and its time delineation were observed, following Joshi's method (*Nature*, 1944, 164, 147; *Curr. Sci.*, 1954, 13, 253)

using a cathode ray oscillograph (208B Du Mont). The results for i_D , i_L , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ at the exciting potentials varied in the range 7 to 20 kV, for anode voltages 23.2 and 20.1 kV and tube current 3.0 mA are recorded in Tables I and II, in part expressed graphically in Figs. 1 and 2, in respect of a typical oscillographic record in Fig. 3 (a, b, c). It may be mentioned that out of the results for Joshi effect, using ozonisers of different spacings under varied operative conditions, only one group is now reported.

TABLE I

Variation of Joshi effect with exciting potential in benzene vapour under X-rays.

Below V_m . $pC_6H_6=105$ mm at 27° . Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec.
Source of X-radiations = Coolidge tube. Intensity (tube current) = 3.0 mA.

Exciting potential.	Anode voltage = 23.2 kV.				Anode voltage = 20.1 kV.			
	i_D	i_L	Δi	$\% \Delta i$	i_D	i_L	Δi	$\% \Delta i$
7.44 kV	3	3	0	0	3	3	0	0
7.50	4	8	+4	+100	4	7	+3	+75
7.56	5	18	+13	+276	5	16	+11	+220
7.62	6	26	+20	+333	6	24	+18	+300
7.68	6	27	+21	+350	7	27	+20	+285
7.74	7	28	+21	+300	7	26	+19	+271
7.80	8	29	+21	+262	8	27	+19	+237
7.86	9	29	+20	+222	9	28	+19	+211
7.92	12	30	+18	+150	12	28	+16	+133
7.98	25	31	+6	+24	25	29	+4	+16
			(irreversible)					
8.04	50	34	-16	-32	50	36	-14	-28
8.10	72	52	-20	-27.7	—	—	—	—

TABLE II

Variation of Joshi effect with exciting potential in benzene vapour under X-rays.

Above V_m . Other conditions same as in Table I.

Exciting potential.	Anode voltage = 23.2 kV.				Anode voltage = 20.1 kV.			
	i_D	i_L	$-\Delta i$	$-\% \Delta i$	i_D	i_L	$-\Delta i$	$-\% \Delta i$
8.0 kV	75	52	23	30.6	75	54	21	28
9.0	95	70	25	26.3	95	72	23	24.2
10.0	115	88	27	23.5	115	91	24	20.8
11.0	135	106	29	21.5	135	110	25	18.5
12.0	160	129	31	19.4	160	133	27	16.9
13.0	174	143	31	17.7	174	147	27	15.5
14.0	200	168	32	16.0	200	172	28	14.0
15.0	216	184	32	14.8	216	187	29	13.4
16.0	230	118	32	14.2	230	200	30	13.0
17.0	254	222	32	12.8	254	226	28	11.1
18.0	265	232	33	12.4	265	235	30	11.1
19.0	295	259	36	12.2	295	263	32	10.8
20.0	325	286	39	11.8	325	290	35	10.7

DISCUSSION

The foregoing results show the occurrence of both positive and negative Joshi effect in excited benzene vapour when exposed to X-rays. As is to be expected from general photochemical considerations, the magnitude of the effect is influenced markedly by the hardness and intensity of the radiations.

It is interesting to observe from Table I, the occurrence of a large reversible positive effect, e.g. + 350% at 7.68 kV, decreasing to + 150% at 7.92 kV under 23.2 kV X-rays; while the corresponding values for 20.1 kV X-rays are + 285% and + 133%, i.e. an increase of conductivity by X-radiation at voltages just less than V_m ; the more familiar and apparently anticonventional negative effect $-\% \Delta i$ is maximum near V_m and decreases numerically at larger V, e.g. the results show -30.6% at 8.0 kV decreasing numerically to -11.8% at 20.0 kV (see Table II and Fig. 2) for anode voltage 23.2 kV. The corresponding values for 20.1 kV X-rays are -28.0% and -10.7%. Fundamentally similar results were first observed by Joshi in iodine vapour in the visible range (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, *Chem. Sec.*, p. 70) and subsequently by others in various systems (Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 405; 1949, 26, 553; Deshmukh, *ibid.*, 1947, 24, 211; Shukla, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1949, 53, 1239; Joshi, *B.H.U. Jour.*, 1950)*.

In all forms of discharge, especially the point to plate, the wire in cylinder, and the full ozoniser, a consideration of the current-voltage characteristics of which curves in Fig. 1 are typical, is necessary for the understanding of the discharge mechanism and the associated Joshi effect. In agreement with Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 29, 389) it was observed that irradiation even with the most intense available and very penetrating X-radiations produced no Joshi effect at applied potentials well below V_m , i.e. when the current is entirely capacitive and is given by $2\pi nCV$, where n is the supply frequency, C , the distributed capacity and V , the exciting potential. This represents the initial flat section of the $V-i$ characteristic.

Towards the end of the flat region the oscillograph shows chiefly a distortion due presumably to some of the higher harmonics setting in along with the fundamental frequency. As the voltage is increased the galvanometer (of period $t = 12$ sec.) shows intermittent fluctuations. A glow then sets in, which is initially markedly unsteady and flickering; it subsequently gains in intensity. At this stage the cathode ray oscillograph shows the inception of high frequency pulses and the corresponding current i increases rapidly. The gas now breaks dielectrically and a conduction current associated with the discharge sets in. This is the region designated as the 'threshold' V_m by Joshi (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 118, 137) and shown by him to be of fundamental im-

* It is extremely likely that $+\Delta i$ arises substantially from the photoelectric ionisation by the X-rays. The precipitous inversion of $+\Delta i$ into $-\Delta i$ beyond V_m ; former's occurrence at both small and large V and of $-\Delta i$ at intermediate V, the appreciable decrease of $+\Delta i$, ending under certain conditions, with change to $-\Delta i$, as the intensity and frequency of irradiation are increased progressively in both the X-ray and the visible regions; the much greater temperature sensitivity of $+\Delta i$ than that generally known for the photoelectric effect, as also the results of the favourable influence of increased supply frequency and the presence of polyatomicals suggest that $+\Delta i$ may not be identified at the present stage with the classical photoelectric effect.

portance in the production of $-\Delta i$ (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548) and indeed of any discharge reaction of a chemical and physical type. Further increase of voltage by even a slight extent augments appreciably the current i which becomes more stable and

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

richer in high frequencies (h.f.'s). The glow also tends to be more uniform and luminous though comparatively concentrated near the inner electrode where the field is strongest.

Joshi has shown the dependence of Δi on a number of operative conditions such as the gas pressure, temperature, nature of the electrode surface, supply frequency, 'ageing' under discharge etc., and that the discharge current i depends on the overvoltage $(V - V_m)$ (Joshi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, **23**, 227).

The present series of experiments (under X-rays) have confirmed Joshi's finding of the appearance of the h.f.s at V_m , and especially, the general result with visible light that the $-\% \Delta i$ is maximum near V_m , being linked preferentially with the suppression of these h.f.s (Joshi, *Nature*, 1945, **154**, 147; *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, **14**, 67) and that it declines with much larger V .

It must be emphasised at this stage that $\pm \Delta i$ under X-rays are practically instantaneous and light reversible as in the visible, the last implies that in e.g., $-\Delta'$, the reduction of the current as observed on the galvanometer and of the h.f. amplitude as shown by the cathode ray oscillograph, are restored instantaneously on screening off the radiation. In the positive effect produced just below V_m region, the increase in the current and of the h.f. amplitude produced by radiations revert to the previous low values in dark on shutting it off. In this connection it is interesting to record what may be called 'irreversible positive effect' (Marathe and Bommannavar, *Nature*, 1950, **168**, 890). This was observed at 7.98 kV with X-rays of hardness and intensity corresponding to 23.2 kV and 3.0 mA respectively (see Table 1). It was now observed that the increased current $+\Delta i$ and h.f. pulses produced by radiation persisted even on shutting off the X-rays, indicative of some inertial hysteresis-like effect.

Joshi's theory (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, **16**, 19) of this phenomenon postulates: (a) formation of an adsorption-like electrode layer consisting of ions and excited particles derived from the discharge space and possessing a low work function; (b) irradiation of the system causes emission of electrons from (a); (c) the negative Joshi effect $-\Delta i$ is a space charge effect due to negative ion formation from *inter alia* the photo-electrons from (a) due to capture by the particles in the discharge space owing to their increased 'electron affinity' by excitation. This theory explains the wide occurrence of $-\Delta i$ in electronegative gases, the pronounced influence of 'ageing' and electrode surface condition, and the fact that both at high temperatures and high voltages $-\Delta i$ is reduced due to the adsorption-like layer being impaired by strong heating and intense ionic bombardment at a very large potential, V . Under moderate conditions of gas pressure (p) and applied V , the general result that $-\Delta i$ increases with p/X is explained since p/X determines the probability of electron capture leading to negative ion formation. Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **22A**, 389) has emphasised that $-\Delta i$ is maximum near V_m where the chemical effect of the discharge reaction is minimum. It is, however, extremely likely that even at these low voltages benzene decomposes slightly to give especially at early stages such products as hydrogen, ethane and like unsaturated hydrocarbons (Deshpande, unpublished results) and especially free radicals; these last account for the formation under discharge of such products as diphenyl (Deshpande, *loc. cit.*). These free radicals have a high electron affinity and are favourable therefore for the negative ionic space charge leading to appreciable $-\Delta i$, as observed. It also follows from Joshi's theory that since low V disfavors electron capture in (c), the photoelectrons from (b) and the cumulative

ionisation by their movement under V should give the positive effect, as actually observed to be a characteristic of low voltage excitation.

It is now suggested that the space charge effect causing $\pm \Delta i$ can originate from the behaviour of the positive ions also, besides negative ions in the general mechanism presented by postulates (a) and (b) in Joshi's theory. It is instructive to consider in this connection the analogy which obtains between an ozoniser discharge and the widely studied point to plane corona (Loeb, *Phys. Rev.*, 1941, 60, 714; 1947, 71, 712; Trichel, *ibid.*, 1938, 54, 1078; 1939, 55, 382; Kip, *ibid.*, 1939, 55, 549) and especially the coaxial cylinders and Geiger Muller counter (Werner, *Z. Physik*, 1934, 90, 394; 1934, 92, 702; Wilknison, "Ionisation Chambers and Counters", Cambridge Univ. Press, 1950; Korff, "Electron and nuclear counters", D. Van Nostrand Co., New York, 1949).

The points of difference between the counter and Siemens' type ozoniser are:

(i) Radius of the inner electrode wire r_1 is very small in the former than in the ozoniser. Consequently the region of intense ionisation limited by the critical radius r_c is very near the wire of a counter, while in the ozoniser r_c is extended in the gap and the region of intense ionisation is comparatively near the outer cylindrical cathode. The field gradient in the ozoniser for the same reasons does not show such extreme inhomogeneity as in the counter.

(ii) In the counter metal electrodes are employed, whereas in the ozoniser both electrodes are of glass. This does not materially alter the discharge mechanism as Maze (*J. Phys.*, 1948, 7, 164) has used the counter consisting of soda glass cathode showing similar characteristics as metal ones.

By an analogy with the counter, the possible origin of the current pulses occurring in an ozoniser becomes clear. In both these, the intense field region is characterised by a large amplification at the inner electrode. An occasional electron will have an increasing drift velocity and later causes Townsend avalanches leaving behind a space charge of positive ions during the period the central electrode is positive [the essential argument is not affected materially (Wilkinson, *loc. cit.*, p. 120) by considering the reversed polarity]. This positive space charge reduces the field near the anode, inhibiting initially the growth of the avalanches and finally choking them off completely. Such a mechanism gives rise to relaxation oscillator-like pulses as shown in Fig. 3a. The h.f. pulses in the ozoniser (Fig. 3b), observed with a higher writing speed of a C.R.O., show an unmistakable resemblance with the Trichel pulses observed in the corona (Trichel, *loc. cit.*). The exceedingly rapid collection of electrons, yielding a charge Q during the active time ' t_a ' (of the order 10^{-8} sec.), gives rise to the almost vertical streak, followed by the less inclined curve during its decline representing the comparatively slow movement of the positive ionic space charge during the traversal time, ' t_m ' (of the order 10^{-5} sec.). The positive ions during ' t_m ' gain energy enough to extract a secondary electron from the cathode; this electron in its turn will produce Townsend avalanches and the process repeats itself giving rise to a succession of pulses causing a self-maintained discharge.

The fundamental role of V_m may now be considered. V_m is envisaged as that potential, at which the positive ions being residual from previous Townsend avalanches eject a cathodic electron and make the discharge self-maintained. Since the ejection from

FIG. 3(a)

FIG. 3(b)

FIG. 3(c)

the cathode is a statistical process, it is to be anticipated that V_m , initiating the region of self-maintained discharge, is not sharp but distributed over a narrow potential region, as observed.

Montgomerys have argued (*Phys. Rev.*, 1940, 57, 1030) that the current i in such discharges is expressed by Q/t_m to a first approximation, where Q is the charge collected during ' t_a ' and ' t_m ' is the relaxation time (neglecting ' t_a ' in comparison to ' t_m ' in the denominator). The effect of irradiation may now be considered in two stages during ' t_a ' and ' t_m ' responsible for the mechanism of the pulse.

Irradiation during the Active Time ' t_a '.—During the growth of the normal pulse and the building up of the initial positive space charge to its full choking concentration, a certain photoelectron ejected on irradiation is able to ionise cumulatively in the region between the cathode and r_c leaving its space charge [B] (see Fig. 3c). This is possible due to the enhanced field ($X+X_1$) where X is the field due to the applied voltage, and X_1 due to initial positive space charge [A]. The additional space charge [B] reduces the field near the anode, further decreasing α , Townsend's first coefficient (for ionisation by collision) below its value in dark. Due to this reduction in α under irradiation the charge collected by the anode is $Q_1 < Q$ (in dark).

This accounts for the decrease in amplitude under irradiation leading to $-\Delta i$. Further, the additional space charge [B] produced on irradiation has a screening effect on the initial space charge [A], thereby increasing its ' t_m '. Thus, irradiation causes a decrease in Q during ' t_a ' and a consequent increase in ' t_m '. Both these contribute to a decrease in the current yielding negative Joshi effect.

Irradiation during ' t_m '.—At the end of the active time ' t_a ' the space charge [A] begins to move to the cathode under an enhanced field ($X+X_1$). Photoelectrons ejected during this time move through this enhanced field near the cathode and produce ionisation by collision between the space charge [A] and the cathode. This increases ' t_m ', and hence leads to a decrease in amplitude and the current, *i. e.* yields $-\Delta i$. The increased ionisation also results in the production of "spurious pulses" or pulses of not normal amplitude yielding a simultaneous opposite component ($+\Delta i$) of the net negative Joshi effect. The ionisation of the gas by X-rays also increases the probability of the occurrence of the component ($+\Delta i$). This is supported by the findings of Fenton and Fuller (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1949, 62, 32) that the probability for the occurrence of spurious pulses is accurately proportional to the charge generated in the dis-

charge. This co-occurrence of $\pm \Delta i$ was observed directly first by Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1947, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 25) and recently by Jatar in iodine vapour (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1950, 9B, 283). It may also be mentioned that Loeb *et al.* (*Phys. Rev.*, 1941, 60, 714) noticed in a point to plane discharge that irradiation with the ultraviolet caused either of two simultaneous and opposite components $\pm \Delta i$ to predominate. A suggestive analogue of the co-occurrence of $\pm \Delta i$ has been observed by Bhiday, Bhide and Asolkar (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1950, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 61) in the action of the magnetic field on the discharge current i in excited Hg vapour.

Positive Joshi effect.—As can be seen from Table I and Fig. 1, this positive effect persists only over a narrow potential range below V_m (viz. 7.95–7.98 kV). The discharge in this region is 'non-self-maintained' i.e. the field ($X + X_1$) acting on the ionic space charge is insufficient to give enough energy to the positive ions to extract an electron from the cathode. This can be achieved at the same X , by increasing the ionic concentration resulting in larger X_1 (obtained by the action of light, in this case by X-rays) supplying trigger electrons from postulate (a) in Joshi's theory. The discharge then starts yielding a large pulse height due to an increase in Q . Under irradiation the discharge becomes self-maintained (due to increased concentration of positive ions). But as soon as the irradiation is stopped, the ozoniser current returns to its original position on $V-i$ curve before irradiation. Thus, for the potential region just below V_m ionisation is caused by X-ray photons resulting in the increase of i . The mechanism postulated above finds further support in the experimental observation of Arnikaar and Naqvi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1951, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abs. No. 20) viz. the large positive effect obtained in the visible range with argon-methane filled G. M. counter below V_m . The positive effect persists only over a narrow potential range below V_m . On crossing the V_m the discharge is rendered self-maintained and it is only when the discharge is continuous that the negative Joshi effect can be produced. V_m may also be characterised as the potential at which the positive effect changes to the negative effect.

The Variation of $-\% \Delta i$ with Applied Potential.—Increase of V enhances the concentration of the initial space charge $[A]$, photoelectronic yield is constant for a particular beam intensity and the additional space charge $[B]$ due to it may therefore be assumed constant throughout the voltage range above V_m to a first approximation. It follows from the above mechanism that the relative concentration of the space charges, (B/A) , under irradiation should have the maximum value near V_m and that it should fall with increasing V since A increases in dark with V , and B is approximately constant. This therefore satisfactorily accounts for maximum $-\% \Delta i$ near V_m and its gradual decrease thereafter.

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